

A Study of the performance of Secondary Teachers in relation with their personality factors

Satish Vishnu Chandane

Asst Prof. Appasaheb Birnale College of Education, Sangli

DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.14106755**

INTRODUCTION

Every individual has to do one kind of work or other to meet his needs. Mahatma Gandhi used to say. "The man who does not work has no right to eat The activity which is done to satisfy the needs of a man is called an occupation

Possession of certain traits to a specific extent may lead a person to success and satisfaction in a specific occupation. On the other hand, lack of certain traits also may lead him to success and satisfaction in some other occupations where the possession of those qualities or traits may prove to be hindrance. Therefore, it is essential for a researcher to compare the psychograph of an individual with the profile of the occupation and if they match, success and job satisfaction will be acquired successfully.

Know thyself is very old concept yet applicable to every individual, today The Psychologists have standardized various psychological tests to know oneself better.

Definition of a Psychological Test-

"It is a standardized instrument designed to measure one or more aspects of the total personality of an individual by means of sample of performance." ----Frank Freeman.

Personality tests and personality measures are vastly developed in USA In India also certain personality tests and techniques have been developed. Often undergo in different part time courses in different situations. Hence, it is quite natural that a lot of external factors must be exiting influence on their mode of behaviour The group may naturally show homogeneity rather than heterogeneity

In this research work the researcher has selected the Primary teachers to study whether their personalities match to their occupations or not. To find out personality factors (Patterns) of Primary teachers from KMC primary schools, Kolhapur and to justify their performance is main concern of this research work.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

To study the performance of secondary teachers in relation with their Personality factors.

16 Personality Factors

- A) Warm-hearted
- B) Intelligent
- E) Humble
- F) Frank
- G) Determined
- H) Venturesome
- I) Self-reliant
- L) Adaptable
- M) Careful
- N) Shrewd
- O) Apprehensive
- Q1) Respecting
- Q2) Sound-follower
- Q3) Socially reputed
- Q4) Relaxed

Performance Components (Skills)

- 1. Lesson Plan
- 2. Introduction of content
- 3. Organization
- 4. Presentation
- 5. Explanation
- 6. Elucidation of content
- 7. Mastery of subject knowledge
- 8. Awareness
- 9. Use of teaching aids
- 10. Confidence
- 11. Blackboard writing
- 12. Class control
- 13. Students' participation
- 14. Use of learning experience
- 15. Effectiveness in execution

(3) THE CONCEPT OF PERSONALITY AND ITS FACTORS

3.1) MEANING OF PERSONALITY -

The word personality actually comes from the Latin word 'Persona' meaning mask or covering. This term is variously defined, numerous theories have been arisen to explain it. Because of its tremendous complexity the word personality has been defined in number of ways. The deviation of the word 'Personality' indicates that the personality can be measured from the external traits as well. Some

thinkers do not discriminate between character and personality. The character is that aspect of the behaviour of a man which may be right or wrong. It is sum total of person's moral habits. But personality is that part of the behaviour which cannot be either right or wrong. But, in fact, personality is much more than behaviour and external features and complexions.

DEFINITIONS OF PERSONALITY -

Morton Prince Describes personality as " The sum total of the biological innate dispositions impulses, tendencies, aptitudes and instincts of the individual and the dispositions and tendencies acquired by experience."

Mc Dougall defines personality as A synthetic unity of mental features and functions in their intimate interplay."

Muir defines as Personality is the whole individual considered as a whole. It may be defined as the most characteristic integration of an individual's structure, modes of interests, attitudes, behavior, capacities, abilities and aptitudes."

Warren and Carmichael call personality as The entire organization of a human being at the stage of his development."

Allport says Personality is the dynamic organization within the individual of those psycho-physical systems that determine his unique adjustment to the environment."

William Healy describes personality as, "An integrated system of habitual adjustment to the environment particularly to the social environment."

R. B. Cattell defines personality as Personality is that which permits a predication of what a person will do in a given situation."

Tarzlen from the practical point of view, the definition given by Tarzlen is the most useful one. He defined personality from the point of view of measurement of personality traits. In his words, "Personality is sum total of an individual's behaviour in social situation.

THE DIFFERENT VIEW POINTS ABOUT THE PERSONALITY -

a) Layman view point-

From his point of view personality means those qualities of an individual which cast their influence on others.

b) Philosophical view point -

Philosophers are the view that the personality is an ideal perfection. It is self-realization.

c) Sociological view point -

This view point tries to put forward to individual in the background of the society. It says, " Personality is the integration of all traits which determine the role of the status of the person in society."

Personality might be therefore, as social effectiveness.

d) Psycho-analytical view point -

According to Sigmund Freud, The structure of personality is built around the concepts of id, ego, and super ego. This id refers to moral component consisting of a mass of instinctual and biological drives and urges which consistently seek expression, the chief instincts being sexual and libidinal.

Thus, this chapter discusses about personality, it's meaning, definitions and some of the viewpoints of it.

3.2) SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PAPER--

Every individual possesses certain personality traits, abilities, interests, aptitudes and other important characteristics. To become a happier man, a more useful person, a more effective worker, each individual must know what are his abilities, interests and personality abilities, interests and personality traits. He must be aware of different biological and sociological factors of his personality. Hence it is quite essential to measure all the natural endowment possessed by the individual, besides his personality traits and other characteristics. In occupational success and job satisfaction the role of individual's potentialities has become very clear and important. According to Donald Super and Mortin John (Jr.) "Square pegs into square holes and round pegs into round holes is the popular concept of finding out such jobs which will suit the interest, temperaments, aptitudes and abilities of an individual.

Ginsburg says" Vocational guidance is nothing but proper utilization of human resources"

V. G. Bureau USA" Vocational guidance is the process to assist an individual to choose an occupation, prepare for it, enter upon and progress in it. Its prominent concern is to effect satisfactory Vocational Adjustment."

'No two individuals are alike' at the same time 'No two jobs are alike' every job needs the personnel's which match the job qualities and skills.'

To find out the Performance of Primary teachers in relation with their personality factors may help to the Govt. and private educational departments to recruit right and proper personnel on the jobs of primary teachers in the schools, while arranging Entrance Tests such factors may play very important role.

(4) OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY –

- 1) To study the personality factors / traits of the secondary teachers
- 2) To study the performance of the secondary teachers with their personality factors.
- 3) To find out the essential potentials (Personality Factors) present in the primary teachers.
- 4) To evaluate the level of primary teachers on the basis of the personality factors present in them and to determine their optimum performance as the primary teachers.

(S) DIFFERENT VARIABLES RELATED TO THE STUDY PAPER

- 1) **PERFORMANCE:** "The act or action of completing given task successfully".
- 2) **PERSONALITY-** "Personality is the sum total of the biological innate dispositions impulses, tendencies, attitudes and instincts of the individual and the dispositions and tendencies acquired by experience".
-----Morton Prince.
- 3) **FACTORS-** "Factors are the attributes or characteristics found within the personality of an individual".
- 4) **SECONDARY TEACHERS** -Primary teachers are the teachers who teach 1st to 7th Classes in the primary schools and having minimum qualification H. S.C., D. Ed.
- 5) **SMC Secondary schools** - Sangli Municipal Corporation primary schools which are run and administered by the Educational Board of Kolhapur Municipal Corporation.

6) Sangli – Sangli is one of the big commercial cities situated in the western part of Maharashtra on the Bank of river Krishna

HYPOTHESIS

Hypothesis -

“The secondary teachers perform well ascending to their personality factors and performance skills”

6.1) ASSUMPTIONS -

Every person has got it's own personality. Personality contains many traits. Researcher is interested in studying the performance of primary teachers in relation with their personality factors. The IVGS 16 P. F. personality test and Observation Scheduled are used to examine the following assumptions.

Whether the secondary teachers are -

- 1) Performing well as per the performance skills (activities)
- 2) Warm-hearted out-going, participating and kind.
- 3) Intelligent
- 4) Emotionally stable
- 5) Humble, mild, conforming.
- 6) Cheerful, talkative, frank, expressive
- 7) Preserving, responsible, playful
- 8) Socially bold, venturesome
- 9) Good team worker, uncompetitive
- 10) Cautious, Compromising.
- 11) Self-controlled, relaxed, frustrated.

6.2) SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY -

SCOPE -

In order to measure personality, it is necessary to measure characteristics of people on scales prepared for all the various traits which form personality. If one starts measuring any single individual he will come across two difficulties.

The number of traits is very large.

Many of them say honesty, love or beauty, sophistication will correlate with scales of many other traits. Hence, to overcome these two difficulties, the traits have been classified as (i) Source traits and (ii) Surface traits.

(i) Source Traits -

Source traits are basic attributes from which spring the more overt behavioral manifestation.

ii) Surface Traits -

The overt behavioral manifestations which are observable and describable are called surface traits.

The source traits can be considered a more stable underlying influence causing certain surface traits. Thus, source traits may be considered to be the dimensions along which personality can be measured and variations along which will give rise to the characterizations of people and the behavior that a researcher observes in the surface traits.

LIMITATIONS -

- 1) This research is limited to 125 secondary teachers of S.M.C. secondary Schools, Sangli
- 2) Researcher is interested in studying the performance of the secondary teachers in relation with their 16 personality factors.
- 3) The research is limited to 50 SMC primary schools only.

7.1) INTRODUCTION –

This research is descriptive survey type research. This type of research generally requires tools like observation etc. As a researcher is interested in finding out personality factors of primary teachers he has administered the IVGS- 16 P.F. personality test which is already standardized and to justify their performance with the help of observation schedule is used.

With the help of these tools the researcher has gathered the relevant data to infer about the personality factors of primary teachers and their performance.

WORK DONE IN THE FIELD OF PERSONALITY RESEARCH IN INDIA -

The Manovigyan Shala, U. P. Allahabad has prepared an adaptation of World test. An Indian adaptation of Resenzweinf picture frustration study for children was prepared by Uday Pareek. The department of Psychology, University of Madras has a verbal projection test. It's author is T. E. Shanmugan.

Mr. B. Krishna of University of Mysore has already standardized a questionnaire to assess the personality in India.

For the use of Tamil speaking students from Tamilnadu T. E. Shanmugan has developed the personality test.

Institute of Vocational Guidance and Selection, Mumbai has developed IV GS-16 P. F. personality test on the guidelines of R.

B. Cattell's 16 P. F. Test.

The psychological research Wing Ministry of Defence, Government of India has also done very useful work in the area of personality tests and the techniques of personality.

A Thematic Apperception test has been developed in Lucknow which is suitable to Indian condition. An adjustment questionnaire has too been standardized for Hindi speaking students.

SOME IMPORTANT PERSONALITY TESTS (INVENTORIES)

1) The Ascendance - Submission Reaction Study -This Test was constructed by W. Allport and Floyed H. Allport. There is one dominant or submissive trait in an individual, the authors contend so, in this test.

2) Bernreuter Personality Inventory - This inventory can be used with college students and adults with success. D. U. Mirchandani has done the Hindi adaptation of this test. It is available from the department of Education women's training college, Dayal Bagh Agra.

- 3) Bell's Adjustment Inventory - This inventory has two forms adults and students. The Indian adaptation of this inventory has been prepared by Bureau of Educational and Vocational Guidance Bihar and Mumbai.
- 4) Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory - The authors of this test are Starke R. Hathaway and J. Charnley M. Ckinley.
- 5) Self-Disclosure Inventory for Adolescents- The test is constructed by Verindra Sinha in 1976. It is in Hindi version.
- 6) H. J. Evenk's Maudsley Personality Inventory It's Hindi version is done by S. J. Jalota, and S. D. Kapoor in 1966
- 7) Dimensions of Temperament- This test is constructed by R. L. Thorndike in America.
- 8) Security Insecurity Inventory - This inventory is standardized by G. Tiwari and H.M. Singh.
- 9) Discipline and Indiscipline Inventory - This inventory is developed by Pratibha Deo & S.K. Bhalla.
- 10) Dutt Personality Inventory - This test is developed by N. K. Dutt in English and Hindi languages.
- 11) Alligarh Adjustment Inventory by A. J. Gadri.
- 12) Adjustment Inventory by H. S. Asthana.
- 13) Vyaktitva Parakh Prashnavali (Hindi) by M.S.L.Saxena.
- 14) Kundu's Neurotic Personality Inventory by Ramanath Kundu.
- 15) Cattell's 16 P. F. Questionnaire –

This inventory has been designed for ages 16 and above. It yields 16 scores in such traits as reserved Vs. outgoing, humble Vs. Assertive, Shy Vs. Venturesome and trusting Vs. suspicious

Adaptation of this test is done by S. D. Kapoor and the Institute of Vocational Guidance and Selection, Mumbai.

A researcher decided to study the Performance of secondary teachers from S. M. C. Schools, Sangli in relation with their personality factors.

Sangli is a progressive district situated in the Western Maharashtra. S.M.C. Primary Schools are in Sangli city situated in different locations. These schools have 1st to 7th standard classes and some have 1st to 4th classes. The schools are run by Sangli Municipal Corporation. The total number of schools is 75. The total number of staff members in the school is 250.

Out of 75 schools 50 schools will be selected. Out of 250 teachers the researcher will select only 125 teachers as a sample. The 50 schools and 125 teachers will be selected randomly by lottery method after making the chits of the schools and teachers in S.M.C. secondary schools, Sangli

Descriptive survey type of method is used for this research. Questionnaire and observation tools are used.

- 1) The observation schedule is used to justify performance of secondary teachers.
- 2) The IVGS 16 P. F. personality test is used to find out personality factors of secondary teachers. This IVGS-16 P.F. personality test is an adaptation of R. B. Cattell's 16 P.F. Personality Test.

7.4) ANALYSIS OF DATA (SCORING) -

- 1) Observation schedule - Collection of Performance data of secondary teachers will be done by observing their lessons. The rating will be done with raw score.
- 2) 16 P. F. test the scoring of the test is very simple and objective. It can be simply done by a punched key. The test is bipolar so that there is no 'right' or 'wrong' response to any item. Both high and low scores have significant meanings except factor 'B'. Every response seen through the punched key is to be given two marks. One mark is given for making 'uncertain'. In factor 'B' intelligence measured, therefore, each item is given one mark. The maximum possible score of each factor is 12. Every factor except 'B' includes 6 items. Factor 'B' includes 12 items. As the factors differ from one another the total score of all the factors cannot be summed up.

TABULATION OF TEST SCORES - By using the following statistical devices.

- 1) Mean
- 2) Standard Deviation (S.D.)
- 3) Norms (Stanines)
- 4) Rating Scale
- 5) T-Test analysis.

8.1) IMPLEMENTATION OF RESEARCH WORK -

1) To implement the research work the researcher visits the school Board Administrator of Sangli Municipal Corporation, secondary schools and gives the letter to co-operate him in his research work and brings the names and addresses of all secondary schools run by School Board of Sangli Municipal Corporation.

2) He will take the authority letter of the Administrative Officer to the Head Masters of various Municipal secondary schools.

3) Then he will meet the Head masters of the secondary schools and request them to make available the staff for taking 16 P. F. Personality Test and he will request the Head Masters to allow him to observe the lessons of the secondary teachers.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- 1) Aggarwal C. Educational Vocational Guidance and Counselling New Delhi: Deoba House), 1993.
- 2) Anastasi, Anne: Psychological Testing (London: Mc Millan Company), 1982.
- 3) Best John, Kehn James Research in Education, (New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.) 1992.
- 4) Bennett, Margaret Guidance and Counselling in Groups (New York: The Robald Press), 1966.
- 5) Crow and Crow: An Introduction to Guidance (New York: American Book Company), 1951.
- 6) Dandekar W. N.: Evaluation in Schools (Poona: Vidhya Prakashan), 1971.
- 7) Freeman, Frank. Theory and Practice of Psychological Testing (New Delhi: Oxford and IBH Publishing Co.) 1965
- 8) Guilford, J.P: Fundamental Statistics in Psychology and Universities (New Delhi: Sterling Publishers) 1984.
- 9) Kocher, S. K. Guidance and Counselling in Colleges and Universities New Delhi: Sterling Publishers), 1984.
- 10) Super, D. E. Psychology of Careers (New York: Harper Row, 1957.